

1 Wine markers in archaeological potteries: detection by GC-MS at ultratrace levels

2 Laura Blanco-Zubiaguirre¹, Maitane Olivares^{1,2}, Kepa Castro¹, Jose Antonio Carrero¹, Carlos García-
3 Benito³, José Ángel García-Serrano³, Julián Pérez-Pérez³, Josefina Pérez-Arantegui⁴

4 ¹ Department of Analytical Chemistry, University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU, Barrio Sarriena,
5 48940 Leioa, Biscay, Spain, +34 946015551, laura.blanco@ehu.eus

6 ² Research Centre for Experimental Marine Biology and Biotechnology (PIE), University of the Basque
7 Country (UPV/ EHU), Plentzia, Basque Country, Spain

8 ³ Centro de Estudios Turiasonenses, 50500 Tarazona, Spain

9 ⁴ Instituto Universitario de investigación en Ciencias Ambientales de Aragón (IUCA), Universidad de
10 Zaragoza, 50009 Zaragoza, Spain

11 Abstract

12 The detection of organic residues that remain absorbed into the pores of ceramic artifacts
13 constitutes a source of information regarding their management. Taking into account the poor
14 conservation state of the potteries and the low amount of the organic tracers together with
15 the main drawbacks to get the relevant information concerning different aspects of past
16 societies, the detection of organic biomarkers is still an analytical challenge. In this work, an
17 improved analytical methodology to maximize the recovery of organic markers related to wine
18 in archaeological ceramics is presented. The developed method consists on the extraction of
19 wine-related organic compounds including tartaric acid, malic acid, fumaric acid, succinic acid,
20 citric acid and syringic acid by means of Focused Ultrasound Solid Liquid Extraction (FUSLE)
21 followed by a preconcentration step by mixed-mode strong anion exchange and reversed-
22 phase solid phase extraction (SPE) and a derivatization step prior to analysis by means of Gas
23 Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS). Finally, the method was applied to real
24 archaeological ceramic fragments (two *dolia*), suspected to have been used to store wine,
25 together with organic residues found inside two *amphorae* from Zaragoza (Spain).

26 **Keywords:** Wine; organic markers; archaeological ceramics; Mixed-mode solid phase
27 extraction; Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry

28 1. Introduction

29 Analytical research in the field of organic archaeological residues found in ancient vessels has
30 grown into a recognized field in its own right and has developed rapidly in recent decades. The
31 characterization of such residues has led to the clarification of several aspects of daily life
32 related to diet, trade, rituals, etc. [1-3]. For centuries, wine has been widely consumed,
33 especially in different regions of the Mediterranean area [4-6], and it has been used for
34 medicinal purposes in China and Middle East [7] or as offering in funerary rituals in ancient
35 Egypt [8].

36 Some small organic acids are widely considered as wine-related organic markers (e.g., tartaric,
37 malic and syringic acid) [5, 6, 9-22] and wine fermentation-related markers (e.g., fumaric and

38 citric acid). For instance, the detection of tartaric acid in ancient ceramic containers indicates
39 that they were used to transport or store wine [8, 9, 23, 24]. However, all these compounds
40 are often labile and not persistent in the ceramic surface being detection at trace levels an
41 analytical challenge [12, 15, 16]. Resins and resin-derived compounds, which are more stable
42 compounds than the previous small organic acids, are also often found in ceramics [6] since
43 they were often used as waterproofing agents or to give flavor to the stored liquid [4]. Many
44 efforts have been done in the literature to develop new analytical methods to detect wine-
45 related organic markers. Folin-Denis and Folin-Ciocalteu methods to determine tannins and
46 polyphenols, respectively, by UV-VIS in amphorae [25] and Feigl spot test to identify tartaric
47 acid in organic residues when irradiated with UV light [7, 17], are some routine analytical
48 methods to detect wine-related organic compounds. However, detection at trace levels is not
49 feasible using these methods and they could also bring false positives as they do not allow a
50 specific identification [12]. Owing to these limitations, hyphenated chromatographic
51 techniques such as liquid chromatography coupled to a wide range of detectors (e.g., diode
52 array detector (HPLC-DAD) [12], mass spectrometry (HPLC-MS) [6, 26], tandem mass
53 spectrometry (HPLC-MS/MS) [8, 9, 17]), and specially, gas chromatography coupled to mass
54 spectrometry (GC-MS), have been widely used in research works dealing with organic acids
55 and other wine-related compounds [5, 6, 11, 12, 15-17, 20, 26].

56 Regardless of the detection technique used, the effectiveness of the analysis relies on the
57 extraction and preconcentration protocols used for the isolation of wine markers. Moreover,
58 the high polarity and solubility of some wine-related organic compounds (e.g., tartaric acid,
59 malic acid, etc.) make difficult their isolation, being critical both the extraction technique and
60 solvent used. Ultrasound bath is by far the most used technique for the extraction of wine-
61 related compounds from ceramic materials [15] but, recently, other techniques such as
62 focused ultrasound solid-liquid extraction (FUSLE) [27], ultrasound micro-bath (UMB) [28] and
63 microwave assisted extraction (MAE) [29] have also shown their efficiency to extract organic
64 compounds at trace levels in archaeological remains. Owing to the wide range of polarities of
65 wine-related organic compounds, mixtures of solvents of different polarities (water, methanol
66 or dichloromethane) have been used in the literature [16, 17]. Some authors suggest the use
67 of pure alkaline solutions (KOH) to favor the cleavage of compound-matrix bonds as it happens
68 with malvidin [15]. Malvidin is a specific marker of dark grape that can be hydrolyzed to
69 syringic acid, which is a wine-related marker but not as specific as malvidin because syringic
70 acid is also present in barley, wheat and even in soils due to microbiological activity [9].
71 Alternatively to the use of KOH to differentiate free syringic acid from that released by

72 malvidin, recently, a two-step protocol based on a first extraction with traditional solvents (i.e.,
73 dichloromethane, methanol) and a second extraction using boron trifluoride has been
74 proposed in the literature [12]. On the other hand, a preconcentration step is almost always
75 required in order to get lower limits of detection. Liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) is the most
76 classical technique used in the literature [30, 31], but the use of more specific extraction
77 techniques such as ion-pair LLE, solid-phase extraction (SPE) [32, 33] and mixed-mode SPE [34]
78 can render higher extraction efficiencies for compounds with a wide range of polarities.

79 Although the usefulness of the aforementioned methods is widely accepted, there is still a
80 need to develop methods that allow the analysis of wine-related organic compounds in
81 archaeological remains with no visible organic residues. The present work describes a
82 thorough optimization and validation of an analytical method to determine wine-related
83 organic compounds (including tartaric acid, malic acid, fumaric acid, succinic acid, citric acid
84 and syringic acid) in archaeological ceramics at trace levels. The method was applied to real
85 archaeological ceramic fragments (*dolia*) from Tarazona (Zaragoza, Spain), suspected to have
86 been used to store wine, together with organic residues found inside two *amphorae* from
87 Zaragoza (Spain).

88 **2. Experimental procedure**

89 **2.1. Archaeological samples**

90 Fragments of two different *dolia* (ca. II-I BCE, labeled as DC4 and DC7) suspected to be related
91 to wine production and collected in an archaeological site found in Dehesa-Cintruénigo (DC),
92 Tarazona (Zaragoza, Spain) in 2015 were analyzed. Moreover, we analyzed two visible residues
93 (labelled as M47 and M48) recovered from the inner walls of two samples of Roman origin
94 found in 2014 in the archaeological site located in Tenerías (Zaragoza, Spain). These
95 archaeological objects were not restored nor cleaned, were stored in the museum of Zaragoza
96 and catalogued as possible wine containers.

97 **2.2. Cleaning procedure**

98 Since the target compounds are prone to be adsorbed in glass material, plastic or silanized
99 glass material was used throughout the experimentation. All the laboratory material was
100 washed with abundant Ellox quality water ($<0.2 \mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$, Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA) and then
101 sonicated under clean acetone (Q.P., Panreac Química, Barcelona, Spain) for at least one hour.

102 After that, the material was rinsed with abundant Milli-Q water ($< 0.057 \mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$, Milli-Q Model
103 185, Millipore, Bedford, MA, USA).

104 **2.3. Reagents and materials**

105 The six wine markers (see Table 1): succinic acid, fumaric acid, malic acid, tartaric acid, citric
106 acid and syringic acid were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). Individual
107 stock solutions from each solid standard were dissolved to prepare approximately $1000 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$
108 in acetonitrile (AcN, HPLC-grade, 99.9%, Sigma Aldrich, Germany) with the exception of
109 fumaric and syringic acids which were dissolved in acetone (HPLC-grade, 99.8%, LabScan,
110 Ireland). All stock solutions were stored in silanized amber glass vials at $-20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. A mixed fresh
111 stock solution containing $20 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of all target compounds was prepared monthly in
112 acetonitrile, whereas intermediate dilutions were prepared daily according to the
113 experimentation.

114 The solvents ethyl acetate (EtOAc), acetone, propan-2-ol (IPA), dichloromethane (DCM),
115 methanol (MeOH) and acetonitrile (AcN) (all HPLC grade, 99.8%) were purchased from LabScan
116 (Dublin, Ireland). Potassium hydroxide pellets (KOH) were supplied by Merck (Darmstadt,
117 Germany). The derivatization reagent N,O-bis(trimethyl)silyltrifluoro-acetamide containing 1%
118 trimethylchlorosilane (BSTFA + 1% TMCS) and the tetrabutylammonium bromide (TBA) were
119 acquired from Sigma-Aldrich (Milan, Italy). OASIS-MAX (poly(divinylbenzene-co-N-
120 vinylpyrrolidone) + quaternary amine polymer, 150 mg) and OASIS-HLB (N-vinylpyrrolidone and
121 divinylbenzene, 200 mg) SPE cartridges were purchased from Waters (Milford, USA).

122 The ceramic models used during the optimization and validation of the methodology were
123 prepared and supplied by the Department of Sculpture of the Fine Arts Faculty from the
124 University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU). The models were prepared according to a
125 previous work [28].

126 **2.4. Sample preparation**

127 Special care was taken in all analytical steps including sample crushing, fractionation and
128 extraction to avoid any cross-contamination. In the case of ceramic samples DC4 and DC7, sub-
129 samples were taken both from the inner wall surface and from the cross section of the ceramic
130 fragments using a scalpel. For samples M47 and M48, the residues were crushed in the mortar
131 in order to obtain a fine powder. All samples were weighed and stored in glass vessels for their
132 preservation until their analysis. 1-g ceramic subsamples (DC4 and DC7) and 0.5-g residues
133 (M47 and M48) were analyzed in triplicate.

134 **2.5. Extraction of wine markers**

135 According to the literature, KOH (1M, aq.) [15, 20] or a mixture of a non-polar solvent
136 (dichloromethane, chloroform, etc.) and MeOH using a ratio of 2:1 v/v [6, 16, 17] are the most
137 preferred conditions to extract wine markers. However, due to the wide range of polarities of
138 the target compounds, the efficiency of several extraction solvents was evaluated: H₂O, KOH
139 (1M, aq.), 0.1% formic acid in H₂O:MeOH (4:1, v/v), DCM: MeOH (2:1, v/v), AcN:H₂O (1:1, v/v)
140 and AcN:H₂O (2:1, v/v).

141 Briefly, 1 g of the synthetic ceramic was spiked with ~0.85 µg of the target compounds and
142 subjected to extraction by means of ultrasound micro bath (UMB). The assays were carried out
143 using a Bandelin Sonopuls HD 3100 sonifier ultrasonic cell disruptor/homogenizer (100 W, 20
144 kHz; Bandelin Electronic, Berlin, Germany) with a cup booster BR made of stainless steel. The
145 extraction process variables (i.e., duty cycle, sonication amplitude and extraction time) were
146 fixed according to a previous work [27]. Wine related compounds were extracted from
147 ceramics using 3 mL of the solvents under study, immersed in an ice-water bath for 4 min
148 using a duty cycle of 0.5 s·s⁻¹ and a sonication amplitude of 20%. Two consecutive extractions
149 were performed using fresh extraction solvents to ensure a quantitative extraction of the
150 target compounds. After the extraction procedure, the extracts were centrifuged, filtered
151 through 0.45-µm PTFE disks and subjected to a LLE according to Pecci et al. [15]. Briefly, all the
152 extracts (except those in KOH, which were acidified before LLE) were directly extracted with 2
153 mL of EtOAc and vortexed for 2 min, and the organic layer containing the target compounds
154 was recovered. The process was carried out in triplicate. The extracts were combined, dried
155 under a gentle stream of nitrogen (Turbovap® LV, Caliper, Life sciences, USA) and derivatized
156 with 20 µL of BSTFA and 150 µL of EtOAc at 70 °C for 30 min before being analyzed by means
157 of GC-MS.

158 The efficiency of the UMB and FUSLE was assessed according to the results obtained in the
159 previous assays. To this aim, 1 g of the synthetic ceramic was spiked with ~0.85 µg of the
160 target compounds and extracted with 7 mL of the optimum extraction solvent using FUSLE and
161 extraction conditions fixed according to a previous work (4 min, duty cycle of 0.5 s·s⁻¹ and 20%
162 amplitude) [27].

163 **2.6. Preconcentration of wine markers**

164 **2.6.1. Liquid-liquid extraction**

165 Owing to the wide range of polarities of the target compounds (i.e., from tartaric acid ($\log K_{ow} =$
166 -1.32) to syringic acid ($\log K_{ow} = 1.01$)) the efficiency of LLE using four extraction solvents
167 combining ethyl acetate (EtOAc) and propan-2-ol (IPA) was studied: EtOAc (100%), EtOAc:IPA
168 (95:5, v/v), EtOAc:IPA (90:10, v/v) and EtOAc:IPA (80:20, v/v). For this purpose, an aqueous
169 solution containing $\sim 0.85 \mu\text{g}$ of the target compounds was acidified with HCl (to $\text{pH} = 1$) and
170 extracted with 2 mL of the solvents under study by vortexing for 2 min ($3 \times 2 \text{ mL}$). The organic
171 phases were combined, dried under a gentle stream of nitrogen, derivatized ($20 \mu\text{L}$ of BSTFA,
172 $150 \mu\text{L}$ of EtOAc, 30 min, $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and analyzed by GC-MS.

173 **2.6.2. Solid phase extraction (SPE)**

174 Reversed-phase SPE (RP-SPE) and mixed-mode SPE were also tested to preconcentrate the
175 target compounds. For this purpose, aliquots of 5 mL of Milli-Q water were fortified with
176 $\sim 0.85 \mu\text{g}$ of the target analytes and subjected to the SPE procedure in triplicate.

177 For RP-SPE, 5 mL of spiked Milli-Q water were loaded onto 200-mg OASIS HLB cartridges,
178 which were previously conditioned with 5 mL of EtOAc and 5 mL of acidified Milli-Q water
179 ($\text{pH} = 1$). Afterwards, 5 mL of acidified Milli-Q water was added as washing step and the
180 cartridge was completely dried for 2 h under vacuum and the analytes were eluted with 6 mL
181 of EtOAc.

182 For mixed-mode SPE, aliquots of 5 mL of spiked Milli-Q water were loaded onto 150-mg Oasis
183 MAX cartridges (mixed-mode strong anion exchanger). Before sample loading, the cartridges
184 were conditioned with 5 mL of AcN and 5 mL of Milli-Q water. The adjustment of pH of the
185 sample was not required since all the target compounds were in the ionized form at $\text{pH} \sim 7$.
186 After the sample loading, 5 mL of Milli-Q water and 5 mL of AcN were added to eliminate
187 interferences. The cartridges were completely dried for 1 h under vacuum before recovering
188 the analytes with 5 mL of 0.8% HCl in AcN.

189 The recovered extracts in both preconcentration strategies were concentrated to dryness
190 under a gentle stream of nitrogen at $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, reconstituted in $150 \mu\text{L}$ of EtOAc and derivatized
191 with $20 \mu\text{L}$ of BSTFA ($70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 30 min) prior to the GC-MS.

192 **2.7. Derivatization**

193 The variables affecting the derivatization step such as derivatization solvent (100% EtOAc and
194 25:75 EtOAc:AcN), temperature ($60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $70 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $80 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and time (30, 60 and 90 min) were
195 optimized, whereas derivatization reagent (BSTFA + 1%TMCS) and volume ($20 \mu\text{L}$) were fixed

196 according to previous works [28]. Under optimum conditions, the extracts were evaporated to
197 dryness in chromatographic amber vials and derivatized with 20 μL of BSTFA + 1% TMCS and
198 150 μL of EtOAc at 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30 min.

199 **2.8. GC-MS analysis**

200 Separation and detection of the derivatized extracts was performed in a 6890N gas
201 chromatograph (Agilent Technologies, Avondale, PA, USA) equipped with an Agilent 5973N
202 electron impact ionization mass spectrometer using an Agilent 7683 autosampler. 2 μL were
203 injected in splitless mode at 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a capillary column HP-5MS (30 m x 0.25 mm, 0.25 μm ,
204 Agilent Technologies). Hydrogen (AD-1020 Hydrogen Generator, Cinel Strumenti Scientifici,
205 Padova, Italy) was used as a carrier gas at a constant flow of 1.5 $\text{mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The following oven
206 temperature program was used for the separation of the target analytes: 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (hold 4 min),
207 temperature increase at 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ to 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (hold 3 min), a second temperature increase at
208 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ to 220 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to continue rising temperature at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ to 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (hold 5 min).

209 The mass spectrometer worked in the electron impact mode with a potential difference of 70
210 eV. The MS transfer line temperature was kept at 310 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the ion source and quadrupole
211 temperatures were maintained at 230 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively. Detection was carried out
212 both in the scan (50-450 m/z) and in the selected ion monitoring (SIM) modes. The m/z values
213 of the fragment ions monitored in the SIM mode are listed in Table 1. The first ion was used as
214 quantifier, whereas the second and third ions were considered as qualifiers.

215 **3. Results and discussion**

216 **3.1. Optimization of the derivatization step**

217 Several variables, such as the nature and volume of derivatization reagent, the nature of
218 derivatization solvent and derivatization time and temperature can affect the efficiency of the
219 derivatization reaction. According to the literature, BSTFA was used in this work [4, 12, 15-17,
220 20, 26].

221 EtOAc has been reported in literature as an adequate derivatization solvent [28]. Nevertheless,
222 the addition of a small percentage of acetonitrile has shown to be effective in order to favor
223 the derivatization process of polar compounds [31]. Thus, the use of 150 μL of 100% of EtOAc
224 and a mixture of 75:25 v/v EtOAc:AcN was tested under fixed derivatization conditions (i.e., 20
225 μL of BSTFA + 1% TMCS, 30 min, 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). The use of 100% EtOAc rendered better

226 chromatographic responses for all the target compounds, hence, it was fixed for further
227 experiments (see Figure 1a).

228 Regarding derivatization temperature, assays were performed at 60 °C, 70 °C and 80 °C for 30
229 min. As shown in Figure 1b, the lowest (60 °C) and the highest (80 °C) tested temperatures
230 meant lower chromatographic signals and poorer repeatability in comparison to the ones
231 obtained at 70 °C for all the target compounds. Consequently, 70 °C was fixed as optimum
232 derivatization temperature for subsequent analysis.

233 Finally, in order to evaluate the influence of time on the derivatization reaction, the extracts
234 were derivatized using 20 µL of BSTFA + 1% TMCS and 150 µL of EtOAc at 70 °C for 30, 60 and
235 90 min. As it can be observed in Figure 1c, no statistical differences were found for the studied
236 time intervals, so that 30 minutes were chosen as optimum derivatization time in order to
237 shorten the analytical procedure. To sum up, the silylation was performed using 20 µL of
238 BSTFA + 1% TMCS and 150 µL of EtOAc at 70 °C for 30 min.

239 **3.2. Optimization of the extraction of wine markers from solid matrix**

240 **3.2.1. Selection of extraction solvent**

241 Several extraction solvents were evaluated to extract wine-related compounds based on the
242 physicochemical properties of the target compounds. On the one hand, polar compounds such
243 as tartaric, citric or malic acids require the use of polar solvents (H₂O, 0.1% formic acid in
244 H₂O:MeOH (4:1, v/v)). Aqueous KOH (1 M) is necessary to ensure the hydrolysis of malvidin to
245 syringic acid, but it may not be adequate for the rest of the target compounds. Finally, less
246 polar solvents such as DCM:MeOH (2:1, v/v), AcN:H₂O (1:1, v/v) and AcN:H₂O (2:1, v/v) can be
247 more adequate to extract those slightly less polar compounds (fumaric and succinic acids),
248 together with the less polar syringic acid. Hence, the efficiency of all these solvents to extract
249 target compounds from the synthetic ceramic sample was tested.

250 Figure 2 shows the chromatographic responses obtained for the target compounds extracted
251 with the different solvents. Overall, the use of mixtures of polar/non-polar solvents (i.e.,
252 DCM:MeOH (2:1, v/v) or AcN:H₂O (1:1 and 2:1, v/v)) rendered better responses for all target
253 compounds in comparison to the use of polar solvents (i.e., H₂O, KOH (1M, aq.) or H₂O:MeOH
254 (4:1 v/v, 0.1% formic acid)). Moreover, polar solvents are not adequate to extract syringic acid.
255 Poor extraction recoveries were obtained for fumaric acid using DCM:MeOH, so that AcN:H₂O
256 (2:1, v/v) was selected as optimum extraction solvent in order to: (i) get the highest extraction

257 efficiencies for all the target compounds, and (ii) reduce water content that can promote the
258 extraction of other ionic interfering compounds.

259 It is noteworthy that, according to the literature, the use of KOH (1 M, aq.) is required to
260 hydrolyze malvidin to free syringic acid [7]. Hence, in order to determine all wine specific
261 markers in the same run, a two-step strategy was proposed. Once the extraction of tartaric,
262 malic, fumaric, succinic and citric acid was over using 7 mL of AcN:H₂O (2:1, v/v), the remaining
263 residue was extracted with fresh 7 mL of KOH (1 M, aq.) by means of FUSLE (4 min, duty cycle
264 of 0.5 s·s⁻¹ and 20% of amplitude) in order to determine the putative content of malvidin as
265 free syringic acid.

266 **3.2.2. Ultrasound micro bath (UMB) vs. titanium probe (FUSLE)**

267 The duality of the ultrasound equipment allowed to make a comparison between the micro
268 bath and the titanium probe. The extraction by means of UMB and FUSLE was performed using
269 3 mL and 7 mL of AcN:H₂O (2:1, v/v), respectively, and using the same extraction parameters
270 (i.e., 4 min, duty cycle of 0.5 s·s⁻¹ and 20% amplitude). The samples were extracted once using
271 FUSLE, whereas two consecutive extractions using 3 mL of fresh solvent each time were
272 performed using UMB. Results were statistically comparable (p-level > 0.05) regardless of the
273 extraction technique used and the number of extractions performed (data not shown). Thus, in
274 order to shorten the analytical procedure, FUSLE was used thereafter.

275 **3.3. Optimization of the preconcentration step**

276 **3.3.1. Liquid-liquid extraction**

277 The compounds in the AcN:H₂O (2:1, v/v) phase after FUSLE procedure can be re-extracted to a
278 small volume of organic phase (LLE), and the organic extract can be easily evaporated and
279 derivatized afterwards.

280 The efficiency of LLE was evaluated using several solvents: 100% EtOAc, EtOAc:IPA (95:5, v/v),
281 EtOAc:IPA (90:10, v/v) and EtOAc:IPA (80:20, v/v). Overall, good repeatability and extraction
282 efficiencies were obtained for the most hydrophobic compounds using EtOAc:IPA (80:20, v/v)
283 by LLE, but poor recovery was obtained for the most important wine marker, tartaric acid (<
284 15%), and for malic acid (< 20%) (see Figure 3). The high polarity of these two analytes makes
285 difficult their extraction from the aqueous media. Moreover, the addition of a 20% of 2-
286 propanol enlarges significantly the subsequent evaporation step prior to the derivatization
287 (almost 90 minutes were necessary to evaporate the extracts to dryness) and, consequently,

288 the analysis throughput. Based on these results, LLE approach was discarded to
289 preconcentrate wine markers and other alternatives based on SPE approaches had to be
290 evaluated.

291 **3.3.2. Solid phase extraction**

292 **3.3.2.1. Selection of sorbent material**

293 The use of RP-SPE (Oasis HLB, 200 mg) and mixed-mode (Oasis-MAX, 150 mg) was studied to
294 preconcentrate wine markers. For this purpose, assays were performed in triplicate spiking 5
295 mL of Milli-Q water with ~ 0.85 μg of the target analytes and following the procedures
296 described in section 2.6.2.

297 According to the results shown in Figure 4a, the dual retention mechanism (i.e., partition and
298 ion-exchange) in Oasis-MAX cartridges in comparison to the partition mechanism in Oasis-HLB
299 enhanced the retention of the target compounds and it was quantitative ($> 80\%$) for all the
300 target compounds except for syringic acid. Syringic acid is prone to be retained by the
301 reversed-phase mode due to its non-polar nature, and hence, slightly higher recovery was
302 obtained for this compound using Oasis-HLB cartridges (75%) in comparison to the one
303 obtained using Oasis-MAX (46%).

304 The results obtained with Oasis-MAX cartridges were compared to the ones obtained with the
305 classical extraction mechanism LLE. As it can be seen in Figure 4b, although acceptable results
306 can be obtained for the more hydrophobic compounds (i.e., syringic acid, fumaric acid and
307 succinic acid), LLE did not render quantitative recoveries for the most hydrophilic compounds
308 including the most important wine marker (i.e. tartaric acid).

309 According to these results, the compounds recovered in AcN:H₂O FUSLE extract were
310 preconcentrated using Oasis-MAX cartridges. Moreover, in order to improve the efficiency of
311 the procedure to determine syringic acid formed after the alkaline hydrolysis of malvidin, the
312 syringic acid recovered in the KOH FUSLE extract was preconcentrated using Oasis-HLB
313 cartridges.

314 **3.3.2.2. Elution profile**

315 In order to improve the recovery of analytes from the mixed-mode anion exchange sorbent,
316 the influence of elution solvent was evaluated. For this purpose, aliquots of 5 mL of Milli-Q
317 water fortified with ~ 0.85 μg of target analytes were loaded onto Oasis WAX cartridges. Three
318 consecutive 3 mL fractions of the solvent (pure AcN, 0.8% HCl) were collected in separate vials

319 to get the elution profile corresponding to a total volume of 9 mL. Afterwards, 5 mL of pure
320 AcN were also loaded and collected separately. All the fractions were evaporated to dryness,
321 reconstituted in 150 μ L of EtOAc and derivatized with 20 μ L of BSTFA + 1% TMCS for their
322 subsequent individual analysis by means of GC-MS.

323 The results of these assays were expressed as the chromatographic signal normalized to the
324 sum of chromatographic responses of each fraction. According to the results summarized in
325 Figure 1Sa in supplementary material, the use of 6 mL of elution solvent was required to
326 recover all the compounds. Moreover, in order to quantitatively elute succinic and fumaric
327 acids (see Figure 1Sb), the addition of 5 mL of AcN was necessary.

328 Similarly, an elution profile experiment was also designed for the quantitative elution of
329 syringic acid from reversed-phase Oasis HLB cartridges. Thus, aliquots of 5 mL of Milli-Q water
330 fortified with \sim 0.85 μ g of syringic acid were loaded onto Oasis HLB cartridges. Four
331 consecutive 3 mL fractions of the EtOAc were collected in separated vials to get the elution
332 profile corresponding to a total volume of 12 mL. According to the results, 6 mL of EtOAc were
333 required to quantitatively elute the syringic acid.

334 **3.3.2.3. Matrix effect**

335 The extraction efficiency can be affected by the composition of the sample since high levels of
336 anions co-extracted with the target compounds from the ceramic sample may compete in the
337 anion-exchange process occurring in the mixed-mode sorptive material. Therefore, the
338 efficiency of the mixed-mode SPE was tested using the synthetic ceramic samples spiked with
339 the target compounds and extracted with the solvent fixed as optimum (i.e., 7 mL AcN:H₂O
340 (2:1, v/v)).

341 The matrix effect during the preconcentration step was evaluated by the comparison of a
342 FUSLE synthetic ceramic sample extract (n=3) spiked with \sim 0.85 μ g of the target compounds
343 before the mixed-mode SPE step with the FUSLE clean solvent extract (n=3) spiked with the
344 same mass of the target compounds.

345 When calculating the ratio between the recovery of the analytes achieved in presence and in
346 absence of matrix interferences, the most affected compounds by the co-extracted interfering
347 anions were the most polar target compounds (i.e., tartaric and citric acid), whereas no effect
348 was observed for the rest of the compounds. Anyhow, since the ratio for all the target analytes
349 was between 75% and 114% for all the target analytes, matrix effect during the
350 preconcentration using mixed-mode Oasis MAX cartridges can be considered negligible.

351 3.4. SPE-GC-MS method validation

352 The main figures of merit of the analytical procedure can be found in Table 2. External
353 calibration curves were built from standard solutions at $\text{ng}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ concentration levels in the
354 range of 0.5 to $10\ \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ for all the target compounds and derivatized in 150 μL of EtOAc and
355 20 μL BSTFA + 1% TMSC and analyzed by means of GC-MS. Linearities were found to be good
356 with determination coefficients (r^2) in the range 0.9950-0.9997 for all the trimethylsilylated
357 wine markers under study. The workflow of the procedure to analyze wine-related organic
358 compounds is shown in Figure 5.

359 The accuracy of the whole analysis procedure for the determination of all wine-related
360 compounds (except malvidin) was determined in terms of recovery using 1 g of ceramic model
361 fortified with 0.85 μg of the aforementioned wine markers. The fortified ceramics were first
362 treated with 7 mL of AcN:H₂O (2:1, v/v), the extracts were submitted to mixed-mode SPE
363 preconcentration and finally, wine markers were analyzed by GC-MS after derivatization.
364 Acceptable recoveries were obtained for succinic and fumaric acids, 100% and 86%
365 respectively, whereas low recoveries were obtained for malic, tartaric and citric acids (in the
366 range of 22% and 34%) (see Table 2). Tartaric, malic and citric acids (all with hydroxyl
367 substituents) are prone to be more deeply impregnated and strongly bonded to the clay
368 structure (i.e., via hydrogen bonds). Therefore, the low absolute recoveries obtained for these
369 compounds may be related to the weak efficiency of AcN:H₂O mixture and ultrasound energy
370 to cleavage the bonds between the compounds and the matrix. In order to correct the
371 extraction efficiency, the use of 3-hydroxy-3-methyl-pentadienoic acid, a substituted
372 dicarboxylic acid of similar nature, as surrogate was evaluated. This compound was added at
373 the beginning of the whole procedure together with the target compounds. Adequate
374 apparent recoveries (> 80%) were obtained after correcting the concentration of the target
375 compounds with the surrogate (see Table 2).

376 The remaining fortified ceramic samples were re-extracted with 7 mL of KOH, and although
377 malvidin was not present in the matrix, the absolute recovery for syringic acid was evaluated.
378 It was observed that in presence of matrix the recovery decreased up to 47% and it could not
379 be corrected with 3-hydroxy-3-methyl-pentadienoic acid. Even so, the obtained absolute
380 recovery was still much better than those obtained after performing LLE (12%).

381 Method repeatability was calculated in terms of relative standard deviation (% RSD) (see Table
382 2) and adequate % RSD values, between 1-10%, were obtained for all the target analytes.

383 The whole method was performed without using solid matrices but all the organic solvents and
384 steps involved in order to calculate procedural limits of detection (LOD_{proc}) as the average
385 signal of blank ($n=3$) plus three times its standard deviation. In the case that no signal was
386 detected at the corresponding retention time, LOD_{proc} were referred to a ratio signal-to-noise
387 of 3. The calculated limits of detection were estimated considering 1 g of archaeological
388 ceramic sample (recalculations should be performed for 0.5 g of archaeological organic
389 residues). The values of the LOD_{proc} were raised to the range 40-76 $ng\cdot g^{-1}$ but were even
390 adequate to detect them in ancient ceramic residues.

391 **3.5. Application to real samples**

392 The developed method was applied to real archaeological samples in order to detect wine
393 markers. Figure 6 shows the obtained chromatograms in SIM mode for the residue M48
394 (Figure 6a) and the archaeological ceramic fragment DC7 (Figure 6b).

395 Tartaric acid was found in both residue samples (M47 and M48), together with succinic,
396 fumaric, malic and citric acids, being all of them wine markers. These observations supports
397 the archaeological hypothesis and we can suggest that the original amphorae was used to
398 transport wine [15]. The alkaline treatment of the ceramic residues allowed the identification
399 of syringic acid derived from malvidin, which reveals the red grape origin of the wine.
400 Moreover, two tricyclic diterpenoid acids were detected in these samples: dehydroabiatic acid
401 and 7-oxo-dehydroabiatic acid. Dehydroabiatic acid and its oxidation by-product, 7-oxo-
402 dehydroabiatic acid, are characteristic compounds of a resin from Pinaceae family, and they
403 have been widely detected in archaeological ceramics or glass containers [16, 35, 36]. The use
404 of pine resin is documented not only as sealant or waterproofing material, but also as
405 medicine, antiseptic or balms used in rituals [1]. Nevertheless, when pine resin is detected
406 together with wine markers, it is thought that it was intentionally used to coat the interior
407 surface of the ceramic artifacts, making it less porous [6, 15, 20], or to act as antioxidant
408 promoting wine preservation or flavor enhancement [9, 16, 30, 37].

409 All the analyzed organic acids (i.e. tartaric, fumaric, succinic, malic and citric acids) were
410 detected in the potsherds DC4 and DC7 confirming their use as wine storing devices. Syringic
411 acid was also found in both archaeological ceramics after the alkaline treatment being its
412 concentration higher than the one found in the residues (see Figure 6b). Pine resin biomarkers
413 were not found in the potsherds. In the case of sample DC7, in addition to wine related
414 markers, high concentrations of oleic acid (C18:1), together with palmitic (C16:0), stearic
415 (C18:0) and azelaic (C9 diacid) acids, and low levels of linoleic acid (C18:2) were also found (see

416 Figure 6b), which are characteristic compounds of vegetable oils [4, 38]. These data suggest
417 that the archaeological ceramic was used for multiple purposes: to store wine but to store
418 vegetable oil as well. Nevertheless, a more exhaustive analysis using a specific methodology to
419 obtain the lipid profile of the organic residues in the ceramic should be performed in order to
420 get more specific information about the vegetable oil.

421 **4. Conclusions**

422 Many archaeologists and analytical chemists have been concerned about the wine use in
423 antiquity and consequently, the search for wine related compounds in archaeological samples
424 has increased during the last decades. Despite several analytical methodologies have been
425 developed to detect these markers, few are the works that focus their attention on the
426 development of analytical methods that ensure quantitative extraction of target compounds.
427 Herein, an entire analytical procedure was fully developed, optimized and validated in order to
428 identify wine markers in visible or absorbed organic residues in archaeological ceramic
429 samples. FUSLE extraction rendered the best results in a single and short extraction time (4
430 min) using first 7 mL of a AcN:H₂O mixture (2:1, v/v) and, then, 7 mL of KOH. For the
431 preconcentration step, mixed mode SPE using a strong anion exchanger cartridge rendered
432 clean extracts, with negligible matrix effect and satisfactory recoveries for fumaric and succinic
433 acids, and also for the rest of the target compounds after the correction with 3-hydroxy-3-
434 methyl-pentadienoic acid as surrogate. Reversed phase Oasis HLB was used to preconcentrate
435 syringic acid formed after the alkaline hydrolysis of malvidin, and even if it was not
436 quantitatively recovered, the recoveries were good enough to detect it in the analyzed
437 archaeological samples.

438 The developed procedure was successfully applied to two archaeological ceramic samples (ca.
439 II-I BCE) and two organic residues found inside the walls of two amphorae (Roman origin).
440 Despite the antiquity of the archaeological samples, all the studied wine markers were
441 detected above the LODs confirming the use of DC4 and DC7 archaeological ceramics as wine
442 containers and the nature of M47 and M48 samples as wine residues. Additionally, the
443 developed procedure allowed to detect simultaneously resin biomarkers from Pinaceae family,
444 which, according to the literature, has been largely used for the preservation of wine.

445 On the other hand, several fatty acids were also identified in the analyzed samples, which
446 helped searching for other uses of the materials under study. In this sense, one of the analyzed
447 samples (DC7) was suggested to have also been used to store vegetable oil apart from wine.
448 However, this analytical method was specifically developed for the identification of wine

449 markers; thus, it should only be used as a screening tool for the detection of fatty acids and
450 more specific analysis should be performed in order to go into detail.

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LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Chemical structure, pKa, log K_{ow} and characteristic ions of wine markers. The first ion (bold) was used as quantifier and the second (and third) ion was used as qualifier.

Table 2. Main method parameters for the developed procedure.

Table 1. Chemical structure, pKa, log K_{ow} and characteristic ions of wine markers. The first ion (in bold) was used as quantifier and the second (and third) ion was used as qualifier.

Compound	Chemical structure	pKa	log K _{ow}	Characteristic ions (m/z)
Succinic acid		3.55	-0.40	147 , 73, 247
Fumaric acid		3.35	-0.04	245 , 73, 147
Malic acid		3.20	-1.11	73 , 147, 233
Tartaric acid		2.72	-1.83	73 , 147, 292
Citric acid		3.05	-1.32	73 , 147, 273
Syringic acid		3.93	1.01	327 , 312, 73

Table 2: Main method parameters for the developed procedure.

Silylation-GC-MS				FUSLE-SPE (MAX)-GC-MS Ceramic spiked at 1.7 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$			
Analyte	% RSD (n=3)	Linearity (r^2)	LOD _{instr} ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$)	Absolute Recovery (%)	Apparent Recovery ^c (%)	%RSD (n=3)	LOD _{proc} ($\text{ng}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$)
Succinic acid	7	0.999	0.01	100	-	3	54
Fumaric acid	9	0.998	0.01	86	-	4	40
Malic acid	6	0.999	0.01	34	123	6	55
Tartaric acid	4	0.998	0.02	22	80	2	68
Citric acid	7	0.995	0.02	28	99	1	76
Syringic acid ^a	8	0.998	0.02	18	-	6	71
Syringic acid ^b	8	0.998	0.02	47	-	10	66

^a FUSLE performed with 7 mL of AcN:H₂O (2:1 v/v) and preconcentration by mixed-mode SPE (MAX).

^b FUSLE performed with 7 mL of KOH 1M and preconcentration by RP-SPE (Oasis-HLB).

^c Extraction recovery corrected with 3-hydroxy-3-methyl pentadienoic acid used as surrogate.

LIST OF FIGURES

- Figure 1.** Obtained chromatographic signals of the silyl-derivatives of the target compounds when optimizing: a) the derivatization solvent (20 μ L of BSTFA + 1 % TMCS, 30 min, 60 $^{\circ}$ C), b) the derivatization temperature (20 μ L of BSTFA + 1 % TMCS, 100% EtOAc, 30 min) and c) the derivatization time (20 μ L of BSTFA + 1 % TMCS, 100 % EtOAc, 70 $^{\circ}$ C).
- Figure 2.** Chromatographic signals obtained during the optimization of the solvent used for the solid-liquid extraction by means of UMB (4 min of extraction, duty cycle of 0.5 s-s-1 and sonication amplitude of 20%) (n=3).
- Figure 3.** Recoveries (%) obtained during LLE with EtOAc and EtOAc : IPA mixtures at different ratios.
- Figure 4.** a) % Recoveries of the target compounds after mixed-mode SPE (Oasis MAX) and RP-SPE (Oasis HLB). b) Comparison of liquid-liquid extraction with optimum solvent mixture with SPE using Oasis-Max cartridges.
- Figure 5.** Schematic flow-chart of the developed analytical procedure for the determination of wine markers in archaeological ceramics.
- Figure 6.** Obtained chromatograms in SIM mode after analysis by GC-MS for a) the organic residue M48 found in the interior walls of an amphora and b) the potsherd sample named DC7. Shortened chromatograms in a frame correspond to the obtained result after performing the second extraction step to identify syringic acid. C_{x,y} are fatty acids of chain length x and degree of unsaturation y.

LIST OF SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Figure 1S. Obtained normalized chromatographic signal of wine markers during the elution profile from Oasis-MAX cartridges using: a) consecutive 3 mL aliquots of AcN (0.8% HCl) and b) a subsequent 5 mL aliquot of pure AcN after elution with optimum amount of AcN (0.8% HCl).